

Mechanistic investigations of oxidation of substituted ethanols by *N*-sodio-*N*-chlorobenzenesulfonamide in acid medium

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The oxidation kinetics of ethanol and substituted ethanols, RCH_2CH_2OH (where $R = H, OC_2H_5, OCH_3, NH_2, Cl$ and Br) by *N*-sodio-*N*-chlorobenzenesulfonamide or chloramine-B (CAB) in the presence of HCl have been studied at 318 K. The rates show first order dependence on [CAB] and fractional order each on [alcohol], $[H^+]$ and $[Cl^-]$. Variations of ionic strength and dielectric constant of the medium and addition of reaction product (benzenesulfonamide) have no effect on the rate. Activation parameters have been calculated. The solvent isotope effect has been studied in D_2O medium. Michaelis-Menten type of kinetics is observed. Mechanisms proposed are consistent with the experimental rate laws.

Organic haloamines contain halogen in +1 state and they have versatile properties, both as oxidants and halogenating agents. Chloramine-T (CAT) is a prominent member of this group and the mechanistic aspects of its reactions have been documented. The benzene analogue chloramine-B ($C_6H_5SO_2NClNa \cdot 1.5 H_2O$; CAB) is becoming important as a mild oxidant and the compound can be easily prepared from benzenesulfonamide and chlorine. Only a few reports regarding the mechanistic aspects of the reactions of CAB are available in literature¹.

The mechanism of the oxidation of primary alcohols to aldehydes by mild to strong oxidants has been investigated by several workers². CAB is an excellent oxidant for performing controlled oxidation of alcohols to carbonyl compounds. Hence, we report here the results of investigations on the oxidation of ethanol and substituted ethanols, namely, 2-ethoxy-, 2-methoxy-, 2-amino-, 2-chloro- and 2-bromoethanols by chloramine-B in the presence of HCl at 318 K.

Results and Discussion

Under pseudo-first order condition, the values of rate constants for the standard run are given in Table 1. Plots of $\log [CAB]_0$ vs time are linear indicating a first order dependence of the reaction rate on $[CAB]_0$. Values of pseudo-first order constants (k') are constant for varying $[CAB]_0$. The rate increases with $[alcohol]_0$ and plots of $\log k'$ vs $\log [alcohol]_0$ are linear with fractional slopes (0.5–0.7).

The rate increases with increasing [HCl] and the plots of $\log k'$ vs $\log [HCl]$ are linear with fractional slopes (0.5–0.8). At fixed $[Cl^-]$ (0.6 mol dm^{-3}), maintained by adding NaCl, the rate increases with increase in $[H^+]$ (which was varied by adding HCl) and the plots of $\log k'$ vs $\log [H^+]$ are linear with fractional slopes (0.3–0.5). At fixed $[H^+]$ (0.1 mol dm^{-3}), the rate increases by the addition of NaCl and the plots of $\log k'$ vs $\log [Cl^-]$ are linear with fractional slopes (0.2–0.4). The slopes (orders) of all the plots are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Rate constants for the standard run and kinetic orders for the oxidation of alcohols by CAB in presence of HCl

$[CAB]_0 = 0.001 \text{ mol } dm^{-3}$, $[RCH_2CH_2OH]_0 = 0.10 \text{ mol } dm^{-3}$, $[HCl] = 0.10 \text{ mol } dm^{-3}$, $I = 0.8 \text{ mol } dm^{-3}$, temp = 318 K

RCH_2CH_2OH	Kinetic orders					
	$10^4 k', s^{-1}$	$[CAB]_0$	$[alcohol]_0$	$[H^+]$	$[Cl^-]$	$[HCl]$
H	3.35	1.00	0.67	0.32	0.25	0.57
OC_2H_5	1.85	1.00	0.52	0.43	0.32	0.75
OCH_3	1.10	1.00	0.46	0.38	0.30	0.68
NH_2	0.21	1.00	0.65	0.44	0.28	0.72
Cl	0.56	1.00	0.53	0.40	0.26	0.66
Br	3.10	1.00	0.57	0.36	0.34	0.70

Addition of NaBr, the benzenesulfonamide (5.0×10^{-4} – $5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol } dm^{-3}$) and variation of ionic strength ($I = 0.2$ – $1.0 \text{ mol } dm^{-3}$) of the medium did not alter the rate. The rate was not significantly altered on varying the dielectric constant of the medium by the addition of methanol (0–40%, v/v).

Studies relating to kinetic isotope effects show that, while k' (H_2O) values are 3.35×10^{-4} and $3.10 \times 10^{-4} s^{-1}$ respectively for ethanol and 2-bromoethanol, the corresponding k' (D_2O) values are 3.46×10^{-4} and $3.20 \times 10^{-4} s^{-1}$. The solvent isotope effect $k' (H_2O)/k' (D_2O) = 0.97$. The reaction was studied at different temperatures (308–323 K) and from the linear Arrhenius plots, the values of activation parameters for the overall reaction have been computed (Table 2).

N-Chloro-*N*-sodiobenzenesulfonamide (CAB) is similar³ to chloramine-T and acts as an oxidizing agent in both acidic and alkaline media. In general, CAB undergoes a two-electron change in its reactions. Depending on the pH of the medium, CAB furnishes different types of reactive species in solution. The possible oxidizing species in acidified CAB solutions are $PhSO_2NHCl$, $PhSO_2NCl_2$ and $HOCl$. If $PhSO_2NCl_2$ were to be the reactive species, the rate law should predict a second order dependence of the rate on [CAB], which is contrary to the experimental obser-

vations. Further, the hydrolysis of PhSO_2NHCl is slight⁴ ($K_h = 4.21 \times 10^{-3}$ at 298 K) and if HOCl is primarily involved, a first order retardation of rate by the added benzenesulfonamide is expected. Since no such effect was noticed, HOCl is ruled out as the oxidizing species. Hence PhSO_2NHCl is the reactive species. In view of these facts, proton catalysis of the oxidation of alcohols by CAB at constant $[\text{Cl}^-]$ can be explained by Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

In Scheme 1, S represents the alcohols, while X represent the complex intermediate species as shown in Scheme 3.

Table 2. Activation parameters for the composite reaction

$[\text{CAB}]_0 = 0.001 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{RCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}]_0 = 0.10 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $I = 0.8 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $I = 0.8 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

RCH ₂ CH ₂ OH	E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹
H	78.2	75.5 ± 0.3	-85.6 ± 0.2	98.6 ± 0.5
OC ₂ H ₅	90.0	87.3 ± 0.4	-55.0 ± 0.4	99.5 ± 0.6
OCH ₃	92.0	90.1 ± 0.7	-53.2 ± 0.3	100.6 ± 0.3
NH ₂	106.5	103.2 ± 0.3	-20.4 ± 0.5	105.0 ± 0.4
Cl	96.2	93.6 ± 0.4	-44.0 ± 0.3	98.0 ± 0.4
Br	83.8	80.4 ± 0.6	-78.5 ± 0.2	97.5 ± 0.5

From Scheme 1, if $[\text{CAB}]_t$ represents the total CAB concentration, then $[\text{CAB}]_t = [\text{PhSO}_2\text{NHCl}] + [\text{X}]$, from which rate law (1) can be derived,

$$\frac{-d[\text{CAB}]}{dt} = \frac{K_1 k_2 [\text{CAB}]_t [\text{H}^+] [\text{S}]}{1 + K_1 [\text{H}^+] [\text{S}]} \quad (1)$$

The above rate law is in agreement with the observed kinetic results.

Since rate = $k' [\text{CAB}]$, equation (1) can be transformed into equations (2) and (3),

$$k' = \frac{K_1 k_2 [\text{H}^+] [\text{S}]}{1 + K_1 [\text{H}^+] [\text{S}]} \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{1}{k'} = \frac{1}{K_1 k_2 [\text{H}^+] [\text{S}]} + \frac{1}{k_2} \quad (3)$$

From the slope and intercept of the double-reciprocal plot, $1/k'$ vs $1/[\text{H}^+]$, the values of formation constant (K_1) and the decomposition constant (k_2) have been calculated (Table 3).

The k_2 for the rate-determining step was also determined by varying $[\text{alcohol}]_0$ at different temperatures (308–323 K) and using these values, activation parameters for the decomposition step of alcohol-CAB complex have been determined by the linear Arrhenius plot of $\log k_2$ vs $1/T$.

 Table 3. Values of formation constants K_1 and K_1' and decomposition constants k_2 and k_2' calculated from double reciprocal plots for the oxidation of alcohols by CAB in presence of HCl *

RCH ₂ CH ₂ OH	$K_1(K_1')(\text{dm}^6 \text{ mol}^{-2})$		$10^4 k_2 (10^4 k_2')(\text{s}^{-1})$	
	A	B	A	B
H	171.7	142.0	12.3	8.2
OC ₂ H ₅	169.2	131.8	7.1	4.5
OCH ₃	278.5	154.5	3.8	3.1
NH ₂	141.8	174.5	0.4	0.3
Cl	186.4	125.0	1.3	0.8
Br	253.6	157.2	8.5	6.2

*A = Values for hydrogen catalyzed reaction at constant $[\text{Cl}^-]$;
 B = values for chloride catalyzed reaction at constant $[\text{H}^+]$.

 Table 4. Activation parameters for the rate determining step calculating using k_2 values

RCH ₂ CH ₂ OH	E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹
H	79.0	76.0 ± 0.5	-94.0 ± 0.3	92.5 ± 0.2
OC ₂ H ₅	89.5	86.9 ± 0.6	-33.5 ± 0.5	93.2 ± 0.5
OCH ₃	91.0	88.4 ± 0.6	-61.3 ± 0.6	99.5 ± 0.3
NH ₂	104.0	101.3 ± 0.4	-02.5 ± 0.4	100.6 ± 0.4
Cl	95.4	92.7 ± 0.7	-30.0 ± 0.4	98.7 ± 0.6
Br	82.0	79.4 ± 0.4	-85.6 ± 0.5	96.0 ± 0.7

The solvent isotope effect studies indicate a slight enhancement of rate in D_2O medium. This is in accordance with the fact that D_3O^+ is a stronger acid⁵ than H_3O^+ . The magnitude, however, is small is a reflection of the fractional order dependence on $[\text{H}^+]$ since a part of the reaction takes place by chloride catalysis and through an acid-independent path. Since the protonation step is followed by hydrolysis involving O–H bond scission, the normal kinetic isotope effect $k_H/k_D > 1$ could counterbalance the solvent isotope effect.

The reaction is catalyzed by Cl^- ion and chloride catalysis at constant $[\text{H}^+]$ can be rationalized by Scheme 2.

Scheme 2

Scheme 2 leads to rate law (4),

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{K_1' k_2' [\text{CAB}]_t [\text{S}] [\text{Cl}^-]}{1 + K_1' [\text{S}] [\text{Cl}^-]} \quad (4)$$

Equation (4) can be transformed into equations (5) and (6),

$$k' = \frac{K_1' k_2' [\text{S}] [\text{Cl}^-]}{1 + K_1' [\text{S}] [\text{Cl}^-]} \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{1}{k'} = \frac{1}{K_1' k_2' [\text{S}] [\text{Cl}^-]} + \frac{1}{k_2'} \quad (6)$$

A double-reciprocal plot of $1/k'$ vs $1/[\text{Cl}^-]$ provides the values of K_1' and k_2' (Table 3).

Oxidation of alcohols by CAB is catalyzed by both H⁺ and Cl⁻ ions and the mixed order kinetics observed in [HCl] can be rationalized in terms of equations (7) and (8),

$$\text{Rate} = k_{\text{obs}} [\text{CAB}] = a[\text{CAB}][\text{H}^+][\text{alcohol}] + b[\text{CAB}][\text{Cl}^-] \quad (7)$$

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \{a [S] + b\} [\text{HCl}] \quad (8)$$

since [H⁺] and [Cl⁻] = [HCl] in aqueous solution. Equation (8) predicts that a plot of $k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{HCl}]$ vs [S] should be a straight-line from which *a* and *b* can be evaluated.

The effect of varying solvent composition on the rate of reaction has been described in detail^{6,7}. It is seen that variation of dielectric constant (*D*) of the medium does not affect the rate. An explanation can be offered in terms of the Born treatment applied by Laidler⁷ for a dipole-dipole interaction, as shown in equation (9),

$$\ln k' = \ln k_0 + \frac{3}{8kT} \left(\frac{2}{D} - 1 \right) \left[\frac{\mu_A^2}{r_A^3} + \frac{\mu_B^2}{r_B^3} - \frac{\mu^\ddagger^2}{r^\ddagger^3} \right] \quad (9)$$

where *k*₀ is the rate constant in a medium of infinite dielectric constant, μ the dipole moment and *r* the radii of the reactants and activated complex. It is seen that the rate should be greater in a medium of lower dielectric constant, when $r^\ddagger^3 > r_A^3 + r_B^3$. On the other hand, $r^\ddagger^3 \approx r_A^3 + r_B^3$ implies the absence of a dielectric effect of solvent on the rate, as was observed in the present investigations, signifying that the transition state is not very different from the reactants.

Structure-reactivity correlations made by attempting to fit the Taft equation⁸ through single parameters σ^* and *E*_s and through the four-parameter form the Pevlich-Taft equations⁹, $\log k/k_0 = \sigma^* \rho^* + \delta E_s$, were not satisfactory. A plot of $\log k'$ vs σ^* is curved (Fig. 1). This suggests a concerted mechanism, the degree of concertedness depending on whether the hydride transfer from the C-H bond to the oxidant is synchronous with the removal of a proton from the O-H group by a water molecule. In earlier work on the oxidation of primary alcohols¹⁰, it was noted that electron-donating groups increase the rate. This indicates that the rupture of the C-H bond occurs ahead of O-H bond cleavage, creating a carbonium ion centre which is stabilized by the electron-donating character of alkyl groups. In the present case (Scheme 3), a decrease in rate with electron-withdrawing groups is in agreement with this observation. The rate of oxidation of alcohols follows the

Scheme 3

Fig. 1. Taft plot of $\log k'$ vs σ^* .

order : H > Br > OC₂H₅ > OCH₃ > Cl > NH₂. A detailed mechanism of oxidation of substituted ethanols by CAB is given in Scheme 3.

It is seen from Tables 2 and 4 that the activation energy is highest for the slowest reaction, indicating that the reaction is enthalpy-controlled. Further, the values of ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger can be correlated linearly (Fig. 2) resulting in an

Fig. 2. Isokinetic plots of (a) ΔH^\ddagger vs ΔS^\ddagger and (b) $\log k'$ (318 K) vs $\log k'$ (308 K).

isokinetic relationship. From the slope, the value of the isokinetic temperature β was found to be 418 K, which is much higher than the experimental temperature (318 K). The relationship was proved to be genuine through the Exner criterion¹¹ by plotting $\log k'_{318\text{K}}$ vs $\log k'_{308\text{K}}$ (Fig. 2). The Exner slope (β) was found to be 424 K.

The moderate values of enthalpy of activation and entropy of activation and the fairly high ΔG^\ddagger values support the mechanism. The near constancy of the ΔG^\ddagger values indicates a solvated state and operation of a similar mechanism for the oxidation of all alcohols.

Experimental

Chloramine-B was prepared¹² by passing chlorine through a solution of benzenesulfonamide in NaOH (4 mol dm⁻³) for 1 h at 343 K. The product was dried and recrystallized from water (m.p. 443 K with decomposition). Its purity was checked by iodometry for its active chlorine content and also by its ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectra. An aqueous solution of the compound was standardized by the iodometric method.

Alcohols (AnalaR) were distilled before use. Heavy water (D₂O, 99.2%) was supplied by B.A.R.C., India. All other chemicals were of accepted grades of purity. The ionic strength of the system was maintained at a constant high value (0.8 mol dm⁻³) using a concentrated solution of NaClO₄ to swamp the reaction. Triple-distilled water was used for preparing aqueous solutions.

Kinetic procedure : The reactions were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions ([alcohol] > [oxidant]) at constant temperature (318 K) in glass-stoppered pyrex boiling tubes coated black on the outside to eliminate photochemical effects. A measured amount of oxidant and requisite amounts of alcohol, HCl and NaClO₄ solutions and water (to keep the total volume constant for all runs) taken in separate tubes were thermally equilibrated for 30 min at 318 K. The reaction was initiated by the rapid addition of a measured amount of CAB to the mixture and was shaken intermittently for uniform concentration. The progress of the reaction was monitored by iodometric estimation of unconsumed oxidant in known aliquots (5 ml each) of the reaction mixture at regular time-intervals. The reaction was studied for more than two half-lives. The pseudo-first order rate constants (*k'*) calculated from the linear plots of log [CAB] vs time were reproducible with ±4%.

Stoichiometry : Reaction mixtures containing varying proportions of CAB and alcohols were equilibrated at 318 K for 24 h in presence of 0.1 mol dm⁻³ HCl. Estimation of unconsumed CAB showed that one mole of alcohol consumed one mole of oxidant,

Here R = H for ethanol, OC₂H₅ for 2-ethoxyethanol, OCH₃ for 2-methoxyethanol, NH₂ for 2-aminoethanol, Cl for 2-chloroethanol and Br for 2-bromoethanol.

The reduction product of CAB, benzenesulfonamide

(PhSO₂NH₂) was identified¹³ by tlc using petroleum ether-CHCl₃-1-butanol (2 : 2 : 1, v/v) as the solvent system and iodine as spray reagent (*R_f* = 0.88). The oxidation products of alcohols, corresponding aldehydes, were determined as their 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivatives and also by using Tollens reagent tests¹⁴.

Addition of reaction mixture to aqueous acrylamide solutions failed to initiate polymerization, ruling out the possibility of involvement of free radicals.

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